

The Psychological Aspects of Caregivers of Covid-19 Patient: A Descriptive Study

Rajalakshmi venkadapathi¹, Prof. DR. J. Jasmine², Prof. DR. A. Felicia chitra³

¹M. Sc. Nursing, Mother Theresa post Graduate, and research institute of health sciences, Indira Nagar, Gorimedu, Puducherry.

²M.Sc. (N) Msn, Pgdh, Mph.D.(N), Professor In Msn, College Of Nursing, Mtpg&Rihs, Puducherry.

³M.Sc. (N) Msn, Ph.D.(N), Principal, College Of Nursing, Mtpg&Rihs, Puducherry.

ABSTRACT

Background: A global coordination effort is needed to stop the further spread of the virus, pandemic is defined as “occurring over a wide geographic area and affecting an exceptionally high proportion of the population, on 31st December 2019”. In this COVID - 19 pandemic situation, the caregiver plays a major role in giving care and giving psychological support through the help of the health professionals.

Objective:

- To assess the psychological aspects of the caregivers of COVID - 19 patients.
- To associate the psychological aspects of the caregiver of COVID - 19 patients with their selected demographic variables

Design: The quantitative approach was used in this study.

Setting(s): The study setting was the selected community area of Puducherry. The researcher selected the community area of Lawspet.

Participants: 200 caregivers of covid 19 patients who were present at the time of data collection.

Methods & Results: The research approach used for this study was a quantitative approach and descriptive design. The study was conducted in the community area of lawspet at Puducherry. Sample size 200 was selected by convenience sampling techniques. The researcher used demographic variables and an assessment scale for the psychological aspects of caregivers of COVID 19 patients.

The result shows that the majority of the caregivers 138(69%) were in the age group of 22-35 years, 145(72.5%) were females, most of the caregivers were married 101(50.5), majority of the caregivers were lived in urban area 103(51.5%), most of them are not received support from the relatives 150(75%) respectively.

The psychological aspects of the caregivers of the covid patients show that 155(77.5%) were having a severe level of changes in the psychological aspects, and 45(22.5%) were having a moderate level of changes in the psychological aspects.

The highest score of the mean value is 12.32 out of the 15 items in the physical and emotional stress domain and the lowest score of the mean value is 10.07 out of 15 items in the family and social isolation respectively.

The results predict that the demographic variables had not shown any statistically significant association between the psychological aspects of the caregivers of the COVID -19 patient.

The study reveals that the nurses need to promote the psychological aspect of caregivers of covid 19 patients.

KEYWORDS: Psychological aspects; caregivers; covid 19; covid 19 patients

What is already known

- Caregivers play a major role in giving care for the covid 19 patients.
- There is some gap to support the caregivers of covid 19 patients.

What this paper adds

- The caregivers have the physical and emotional stress developed while caring for the covid 19 patients.
- The researcher found that the psychological aspects of the caregivers to be promoted

BACKGROUND

Health specialists were clearly on the vanguard of the worldwide deployment against the pandemic cases functioning their duties in various institutes and improving to offer expert care for COVID -19 patients^[1].

Nurses are the lead of COVID -19 case management and confronting serious challenges to have their driving condition improved and the significance of their safety acknowledged.^[1]

Corresponding to the international council of Nurses mortality among nursing staff contaminated with the COVID -19 come about worldwide, especially in countries with a high rate of infection and morality such as the United States, France, sprain, and Italy.^[1]

Nurses drop into the category of full-propelled anxiety reaction syndrome to undergo exhaustion post-traumatic stress syndromes^[2].

Nurse are valuable sources for every single country. Their health level, comfort, and safety are very vital not only for constant and safe long-suffering care but also for control of any illness. Delivering care to COVID -19 patients has been a virtuous experience for nannies that in supplement to the increased assignment may also cause tension in all health professions. Several research studies have reimbursed interest in the psychological problem of the wellbeing care work and the high priority of supplying psychological nursing for those nurses. Though, many qualitative educations have been printed about the skill of nurses in giving care to COVID -19 patients.^[10]

Some studies previously published suggested that the caregiver has experienced many psychological aspects positively and negatively such as impact roving the care, bonding between the family members, emotional stress, anxiety, depression, and social isolation.

According to 10:20 UTC on 12 April 2021 no cases are 136,136,954, total number of deaths 2,938,200, recovery – 77,506,641 people. This number shows the cumulative number of confirmed cases in about 192 countries and territories.

In India 13.5 M cases (169K) recovered 12.2 M, death -170K, in Tamil Nādu – cases 933K, recovered 879 K deaths 12908.

Hence the investigator from her experience observed that many of the caregivers were having some psychological disturbances during the caring of the covid 19 patients in the community. So that the researcher wants to know the psychological aspect of the caregiver of the COVID -19.

This study aimed to explore the perception of caregivers and their opinion about the health care system while caring for the COVID -19 positive person in the hospital and the home.

If the study is conducted on this caregiver's psychological aspects will help to promote the care of caregivers among the covid 19 patients and for the future research on the caregivers' psychological aspects and to improve the care the caregivers in the various conditions. It helps to prevent stress among the caregivers.

METHODS

RESEARCH APPROACH

The quantitative approach was used in this study.

RESEARCH DESIGN

A descriptive research design was used in this study.

SETTING OF THE STUDY

The study setting was the selected community area of Puducherry. The researcher selected the community area of Lawspet.

POPULATION

The population of the study was all caregivers of covid 19 patients who were present at the time of data collection.

SAMPLE

The sample of the study was caregivers of COVID -19 patients who meet the inclusion criteria.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

The sampling techniques used in this study were convenience sampling techniques.

SAMPLE SIZE CALCULATION

The sample size was calculated to be 194 using Open Epi Version 3.01 ($n = [DEFF * Np(1-p)] / [(d^2/Z^2(1-a/2)^2 * (N-1) + p*(1-p)]$), where “p” was considered maximum of 71.8%, absolute precision of 5%, 95% confidence interval and alpha error of 5%). Sample size is 194 we round off 200.

SAMPLE SIZE

The sample size selected was 200 caregivers of covid 19 patients.

CRITERIA FOR SAMPLE SELECTION

Inclusion criteria

All caregivers of COVID -19 patients who are willing to participate in this study.
All caregivers are present at the time of data collection.

Both adult male and female caregivers, aged 22-to 4to 5, were taking care of the COVID -19 patient.

Exclusion criteria

A caregiver of covid 19 patients who is not willing to participate.

VARIABLE OF THE STUDY

The study variable is the psychological aspect of caregivers of COVID -19 patients.

DEVELOPMENT AND DESCRIPTION OF THE TOOL

TOOL TO ASSESS THE PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECT OF CAREGIVER

The Tool which was selected for this study was the assessment of psychological aspects among the caregivers. It is considered the appropriate tool for eliciting the psychological aspect of the caregivers. The tool to developed by an in-depth review of various books. It is the 15 self- structured questionnaires for the assessment of the psychological aspects of the caregivers of covid 19 patients.

DESCRIPTION OF TOOL

This tool consists of two sections namely

SECTION A: Demographic variables

SECTION B: Assessment scale for the psychological aspect among caregivers of covid 19 patients.

SECTION A: It consists of demographic data including age, sex, educational qualification, income, relationship with the COVID -19 patient, marital status, residency type of family, period of contact, and support from the family members.

SECTION B: It is the scale for assessing the self-motivation and physical and emotional stress and social isolation of the caregivers of the covid 19 patients. Each domain consists of 5 questions framed, a total of 15 questions. Scoring was given from 0 to 4.

SCORE INTERPRETATION:

SCORE INTERPRETATION	SCORE
MILD	1 – 20
MODERATE	21 – 40
SEVERE	41 – 60

DATA COLLECTION PROCEDURE

Formal permission obtaining from the current authorities to conduct this study. The information covid 19 affected patients list received from the nursing officer of lawspet PHC and community department. The list was obtained, then the investigator proceeded with the data collection.

Day 1- the investigator selected the family who is affected by covid 19 in the lawspet area door-to-door covid affected family. After introducing to the family, formal permission was obtained from the participants, the data were collected. It took approximately 20-30 minutes for each sample. For one day 8 to 10 families were selected.

The same procedures were continued until 200 samples. The question was given to the participant, and they filled out the form. The investigator helped those who could not do so.

The data collecting procedures were done everyday morning 10- 12 pm.

Data collected were organized under the following sections.

Section A: Description of the demographic variables among caregivers of COVID -19 patients.

Section B: Assessment of the level of psychological aspects among caregivers of COVID -19 patients.

Section C: Association between the level of psychological aspects among caregivers of COVID -19 patients with their selected demographic variables.

SECTION A: DESCRIPTION OF THE DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES AMONG CAREGIVERS OF COVID -19 PATIENTS.

Table 1: Frequency and Percentage wise Distribution of demographic among caregivers of COVID -19 patients.

(N=200)

SL. NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (N)	PERCENTAGE (%)
1	Age (in years)		
	22-35 years	138	69
	36-45 years	62	31
2	Gender		
	Male	55	27.5
	Female	145	72.5
3	Educational qualification		
	Master degree	41	20.5
	Undergraduate	96	48
	Below 8 th standard	63	31.5
4	Income		
	Monthly income	83	41.5
	Daily wages	117	58.5
5	Relation with the COVID -19 patient		
	Friends	48	24
	Relative	62	31
	Family members	90	45
6	Marital status		
	Married	101	50.5
	Unmarried	99	49.5

7	Residence		
	Rural	97	48.5
	Urban	103	51.5
8	Type of the family		
	Nuclear family	147	73.5
	Joint family	53	26.5
9	How many days stayed in the hospital for the treatment		
	Below 14 days	82	41
	Above 14 days	118	59
10	Support from the relatives		
	Given	150	75
	Not given	50	25

Table 1 - Frequency and percentage-wise Distribution of demographic variables among caregivers of COVID -19 patients show that out of the 200 caregivers of COVID -19 patients who were interviewed, the Majority of the caregivers 138 (69%) were in the age group of 2235 years. Most of the caregivers were female 145 (72.5%). The majority of the caregiver has completed b6 (48%)caregivers in undergraduates. Most of the caregivers were a daily wages income of 117 (58.5%) Majority of the caregiver were family members in about the COVID patientsatient 90(45%). Most of the caregivers were married 101 (50.5%). The majority of the caregiver lived in urban areas 103 (51.5%). Most of the caregiver comes from the nuclear family 147 (73.5%). The majority of the caregiver was above 14 days stayed in the hospital for treatment 118 (59%). Most of them are not received support from their relatives 150 (75%) respectively.

SECTION B: ASSESSMENT OF THE LEVEL OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS AMONG CAREGIVERS OF COVID -19 PATIENTS.

Table 2:- Frequency and percentage-wise distribution of level of psychological aspects among caregivers of COVID -19 patients. (N = 200)

LEVEL OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS AMONG CAREGIVERS OF COVID -19 PATIENTS	Frequency (N)	Percentage (%)
Mild (1-20)	0	0
Moderate (21-40)	45	22.5
Severe (41-60)	155	77.5
Total	200	100

Table 2 shows the frequency and percentage-wise distribution of the level of psychological aspects among caregivers of COVID -19 patients. The majority of the caregivers 155 (77.5%) had severe levels of psychological aspects and 45 (22.5%) had moderate levels of psychological aspects. The mean and standard deviation of level of psychological aspects among caregivers of COVID -19 patients is (33.25±7.814) respectively.

Table 3: Mean and Standard deviation of psychological aspects among caregivers of COVID -19 patients. (N = 200)

PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS AMONG CAREGIVERS OF COVID -19 PATIENTS.	MEAN	STANDARD DEVIATION
Self- motivation	10.84	2.308
Physical and emotional stress	12.34	2.930
Family and social isolation	10.07	2.576
Total	33.25	7.814

Table -3 The highest score of the mean value is 12.32 out of the 15 items in the physical and emotional stress domain and the lowest score of the mean value is 10.07 out of 15 items in the family and social isolation respectively.

Fig: Mean and Standard deviation of psychological aspects among caregivers of COVID -19 patients.

SECTION C: ASSOCIATION BETWEEN LEVELS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS AMONG CAREGIVERS OF COVID -19 PATIENTS WITH THEIR SELECTED DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES.

Table 4: Association between the level of psychological aspects among caregivers of COVID -19 patients with their selected demographic variables.

(N=200)

SL. NO	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	LEVEL OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS				Chisquare X ²	df	pvalue
		MODERATE		SEVERE				
		N	%	N	%			
1	Age (in years)							
	22-35 years	31	68.9	107	69	0.000	1	0.985 NS
	36-45 years	14	31.1	48	31			
2	Gender					0.272	1	0.602 NS
	Male	11	24.4	44	28.4			
	Female	34	75.6	111	71.6			

3	Educational qualification					0.299	2	0.861 NS
	Master degree	10	22.2	31	20			
	Undergraduate	20	44.4	76	49			
	Below 8 th standard	15	33.4	48	31			
4	Income					0.012	1	0.911 NS
	Monthly income	19	42.2	64	41.3			
	Daily wages	26	57.8	91	58.7			
5	Relation with the COVID -19 pati ent					1.635	2	0.442 NS
	Friends	9	20	39	25.2			
	Relative	12	26.7	50	32.3			
	Family members	24	53.3	66	42.5			
6	Marital status					2.096	1	0.148 NS
	Married	27	60	74	47.7			
	Unmarried	18	40	81	52.3			
7	Residence					0.078	1	0.780 NS
	Rural	21	46.7	76	49			
	Urban	24	53.3	79	51			
8	Type of the family					0.546	1	0.460 NS
	Nuclear family	35	77.8	112	72.3			
	Joint family	10	22.2	43	27.7			
9	How many days stayed in the hospital for t he treatment					0.712	1	0.399 NS
	Below 14 days	16	35.6	66	42.6			
	Above 14 days	29	64.4	89	57.4			
10	Support from the relatives					0.239	1	0.625 NS
	Given	35	77.8	115	74.2			
	Not given	10	22.2	40	25.8			

NS- Non-Significant

Table 4 shows that the demographic variables had not shown a statistically significant association between levels of psychological aspects among caregivers of COVID - 19 patients respectively.

DISCUSSION

. The study design adopted for this study was a descriptive survey research design. the sample size is 200 samples of caregivers of the COVID -19 patients who were assessed by selfstructured questionnaires. the findings of this study were discussed according to the following objectives of the study.

- To assess the psychological aspects of the caregivers of COVID -19 patients.
- To associate the psychological aspects of the caregiver of COVID - 19 patients with their selected demographic variables.

MAJOR FINDINGS IN THE DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES

The majority of caregivers belong to the age group between (138) 69%. the remaining were (62) 31%.

Regarding gender, most of the caregivers were females (145) 72.5%, and the remaining were males (55) 27.5%. The educational qualification (41) 20.5% of the subjects belongs to the master's degree, (96) 48% of them belong undergraduate, (63) 31.5% of them were studied below 8th standard.

Regarding the monthly income (83) 41.5% of caregivers were getting the monthly income respectively, and (117) 58.5% of caregivers were getting the daily wages.

Out of 200 samples of caregivers (48) 24% were friends, (62) 31% were relatives, (90) and 45% were cared for by their family members.

According to their marital status (10,1), 50.5% of them were married, and (99) 49.5% of them were single.

In residency (97) 48.5% of the subject belonged to the rural area and the remaining (103) 51.5 % of subjects belongs to urban areas.

According to the type of the family (147), 73.5% of the families were nuclear families and the (53) 26.5% of families were joint families.

Regarding the number of days in hospital stay for the COVID -19 treatment in that mostly below 14 days were stayed in hospital (118) 59%. then (82) 41% stayed in the hospital for 14 days.

The majority of the caregiver was getting support from the caregivers (150) 75% and the remaining (50) 25% were not getting the support from their family members.

The first objective of this study is to assess the psychological aspects of the caregivers of COVID -19 patients.

Through the level of psychological aspects of the caregiver of COVID -19 patients, most of the sample was the severe levels of changes in their psychological aspects (155) 77.5 %, and the remaining were (45) 22.5% were moderate levels of changes in their psychological aspects in caring of COVID 19 patient.

The highest score of the mean value is 12.32 out of the 15 items in the physical and emotional stress domain and the lowest score of the mean value is 10.07 out of 15 items in the family and social isolation respectively.

The secondary objectives are to associate the psychological aspects of the caregiver of COVID -19 patients with their selected demographic variables.

The results predict that the demographic variables had not shown any statistically significant association between the psychological aspects of the caregivers of the COVID -19 patient.

Hence the H1, there will be a significant relationship between the psychological aspect of caregivers of COVID -19 patients with their selected demographic variables is **rejected**.

The result shows there was no significant association between the psychological aspects and demographic variables.

Limitations

- The study is delimited to the Puducherry community area of Lawspet.
- The study is delimited to 200 samples of caregivers who have taken care of the covid 19 patients.
- The data collection period is delimited to 4 weeks.

CONCLUSIONS

The study result shows that in the psychological aspects of the COVID -19 patient. majority of the caregivers were in the severe level and the highest score is in the physical and emotional stress and the lowest score is in the family and social isolation domain.

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Conflict of interest

NONE

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